

Question Regarding Quantum Pure State Entropy and the Correspondence Principle Part 2

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In Part I, we considered the $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit (where n is a single particle quantum energy level) and argued that quantum informational entropy $S_x + S_p$, where $S_x = - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*W\}$ and $S_p = - \sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\}$ with $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ should be used as thermodynamic entropy, at least in the particle in an infinite well case. Here, we generalize to any n for a quantum adiabatic transition (which then becomes a thermodynamic adiabatic one if L vanishes from $S_x + S_p$).

We first try to analyze a single classical particle bouncing back and forth in a one dimensional box with constant velocity. In classical mechanics, one follows the particle as $x(t)$, but this is at odds with the notion of information entropy in L (length of box). If one thinks of such a concept, one does not know $x(t)$ and so Newtonian ideas like $\int F dx$ apply only to the edges of the box where x is measured. If some kind of interaction were to occur inside the box (e.g a photon entered and interacted etc), this kind of interaction could be considered as a heat interaction. In such a case, time units would involve numerous cycles of the particle so that any movement of the wall would ensure contact. Thus, there would be two kinds of interactions which could change energy, one dealing with the wall in a Newtonian manner, and the other, with interactions inside the box, associated with heat. We carry this analogy over into the quantum domain.

We suggest that in the case of a quantum adiabatic transformation for a particle in an infinite well, only wall considerations occur and so there should be no heat type energy or $dS=0$ as there are no internal interactions, it seems. We argue that $S_x + S_p$ for an infinite well removes L and so $d(S_x + S_p)$ for a change in L is 0 and is consistent with $dS=0$, i.e. plays the role of thermodynamic entropy in this case.

Thermodynamic Entropy

Thermodynamic entropy appears in the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is usually applied to a gas in a box, meaning there are many particles. If $dS=0$, $dE = -PdV$ has a Newtonian form. We ask whether one may try to apply this scenario to a single Newtonian particle moving in a box with constant speed.

We first note that in Newtonian mechanics, one follows a particle as $x(t)$. In statistical mechanics, one does not follow each particle in a gas through $x(t)$ as there are many, but we suggest that the statistical notion should apply to a single particle. In such a case, for there to be a sense of pressure, time units should involve several cycle units so that if the wall moves, there is guaranteed to be an interaction with the particle in a Newtonian manner. If one does not follow the particle inside the box (hence a spatial information entropy), that does not mean that

interactions cannot occur inside, say with incoming photons etc. Thus, there is the wall interaction which has the form $-Fdx$ because only the wall position is measured in space, but there can be internal collisions which one would call heat transfers. We argue that one may think of a classical particle in a box in terms of the first law of thermodynamics. If the box is held fixed, one may have incoming photons strike the particle and increase its kinetic energy. This would be considered an increase in heat. The reason we suggest such a view is that we wish to apply it to a quantum mechanical treatment of a single particle bound in an infinite potential well.

Quantum Mechanical Picture of a Particle in an Infinite Potential

The quantum view of a particle in a box of length L (from $x=0$ to $x=L$) necessarily involves averages and probabilities and so one may immediately create an information entropy for both p and x , i.e. S_p and S_x , where:

$$S_x = - \int_0^L dx \frac{1}{L} \sin^2(n\pi x/L) \ln\left\{ \frac{1}{L} \sin^2(n\pi x/L) \right\} \quad ((1))$$

C goes as $1/L$.

$$\text{and } S_p = - \int dp P_n(p) \ln\{P_n(p)\} \quad ((2))$$

$$(1) \text{ gives } P_n(x) = \frac{2}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right) \ln\left\{ \frac{2}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right) \right\} \quad ((3))$$

One may notice that for any fixed n (energy level), S_x goes as $c_1 + \ln(L)$ and $P_n(p) = \text{Function}(n) + \ln(1/L)$ ((4)).

Thus: $S_x + S_p = \text{function}(n)$ with no L present.

Specifically, S_x is n independent, but goes as $\ln(L)$ which would also be the informational entropy assigned to a classical particle in a box of length L . As a result, we tried to describe a single particle in a box in a statistical manner. We argued, however, that heat means an internal interaction not involving the wall. In the quantum case, if L is held fixed, then one may move from one n to another via such a heat interaction, i.e. non-wall interaction. For example, a photon could be absorbed and later emitted. We argue that even the quantum single particle bound state has the sense of a mechanical interaction at the wall and a heat like internal interaction linked to photons.

The argument we then make is that if one quantum adiabatically moves the wall keeping the energy level n constant, it seems there are no physical internal interactions and so there should be no overall entropy change. Given that $S_x(L,n) + S_p(L,n)$, if n is constant and L changes then the L dependence of S_x and S_p should cancel to allow for adiabatic quantum transitions which are equivalent to thermodynamical adiabatic processes.

Thus, we argue for S_x+S_p representing a thermodynamic entropy even in the n finite case (and not just in the $n \rightarrow$ infinite of Part I).

The Question of Thermal Energy

We have argued that thermal energy seems to be linked with changing n with L fixed. In other words, thermal energy can be added or released without moving the wall (L stays constant). The question then becomes: What is the ground state energy $E = 1/2m (3.14/L)^2$ ($3.14/L$)? This energy cannot be released if L is held constant and so does not seem to be thermal energy. It is, however, changed by work by adiabatically changing L to $L+dL$ and so seems to be mechanical in nature, but is also linked with an entropy S_p+S_x which is not a function of L , but only $n=1$. Thus, there seems to be some fixed entropy in the system which cannot be removed if L is held constant. One may create a second entropy function based on a fixed L by having interactions with photons linked with the E_n spacings. This entropy is based on the energy level differences, but not on the entropy of the ground state, which is associated with energy which cannot be released if L is held constant.

It seems that even as n is held constant as L changes (quantum adiabatic change), energy changes, but in a structured way, i.e. one which maintains the wavefunction linked to n . This seems to be a reversible process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we argued that S_x+S_p should be thermodynamic entropy by considering a particle in a box and an $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit. Here, we argue that this may be extended to all n values. We consider a thermodynamical view of a Newtonian particle in a box and argue that if one drops the knowledge of $x(t)$, hence introducing a spatial entropy, then only the wall of the box may be described as doing Newtonian work $-Fdx = -PdL$ because one only keeps track of the x position of the wall. Internal interactions, however, are physically possible, but cannot be tracked using Fdx . Thus, such internal interactions are associated with heat. We apply this model to a quantum bound particle in a potential well. We argue that L disappears from S_x+S_p for any energy level and so a quantum adiabatic transition becomes a thermodynamic one because it seems that there are no internal interactions occurring which would be linked with heat, i.e. a change in entropy.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box